

REFLECTIVE ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING COGNITIVE-METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN TEACHING PHILOSOPHY

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the reflective aspects of developing the cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers in the process of teaching philosophy. The study highlights the importance of integrating reflective approaches into pedagogical practice as a key factor in enhancing students' analytical thinking, self-awareness, and independent learning abilities. Special attention is given to the role of reflection as a psychological and methodological mechanism that ensures the effective assimilation of knowledge and its transformation into professional competence.

Introduction. Today, leading scientific research institutes and international centers around the world are conducting a number of studies on the design of students' individual learning trajectories and the development of future teachers' cognitive competence as a result of key competencies. At the same time, ensuring the integrative nature of the process of developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers within the context of teaching philosophy, fostering a continuous desire for self-improvement in future educators, and improving didactic conditions for developing independent cognitive-methodological knowledge acquisition skills, creativity, and the ability to create new pedagogical values are becoming important priorities. Based on this necessity, improving the pedagogical system for developing cognitive-methodological competence in future teachers through the teaching of philosophy is of urgent importance.

Literature Review And Methods. The theoretical aspects, methodology, and effectiveness of developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers have been studied by scholars such as T. Buzan, N. German, M. Bernis, M. Pietra, E. Terhart, R. Dunn, M. Akhmetov, A. Bazayeva, L. Bocharova, E. Vyazovova, T. Dobridina, I. Dulchayeva, E. Zeer, T. Korotenko, L. Osipova, A. Piligin, V. Pustovoytov, S. Roslyakova, U. Inoyatov, N. Muslimov, O. Musurmonova, B. Khodjaev, M. Vakhobov, and M. Mirsoliyeva, among others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Based on the philosophy course, a set of tasks was developed for future teachers aimed at identifying modern problems of pedagogy and personality development, as well as the value-based and content-related significance of pedagogical tasks that support the professional formation of students in higher pedagogical education institutions and the methods for solving them. The essence of this method was

clearly manifested in the implementation of various approaches—anthropological, reflexive, and creative—in solving these tasks.

In discussing the topic “Moral Culture and Values,” students were offered the task of describing various pedagogical theories that differently interpret the interrelation between the processes of development and upbringing. According to the established principle, for some individuals, the image of an independent person is preferable, and authoritarian approaches to education are considered acceptable as a component of pedagogical culture familiar within society. This is explained as follows: although such a form of communication is not considered desirable, it is believed that alternative approaches to organizing the educational process may not always be effective.

To achieve this objective, practical sessions were conducted on the topics: *“What is the harmony between tradition and innovation?”*, *“What is the difference between a successful person and pedagogical success?”*, *“Is it correct to approach any task with material interest or enthusiasm?”*

The essence and significance of the teaching profession were mastered through achieving objectivity and subjectivity within the framework of theory, practice, personal experience, and cultural context. This direction, implemented through students’ work with culturally meaningful texts, is of particular importance. It implies that the learning material is not based solely on textbooks or lecturers’ presentations, but rather on students’ independent and creative reinterpretation of primary sources—works of renowned educators, psychologists, sociologists, social pedagogues, philosophers, as well as representatives of science and art. At the same time, it should be noted that axiological texts perform a role beyond the real text context, serving as models of activity and, in some cases, reflecting real-life (pedagogical) situations.

All stages of the technology were implemented using methods that enable the interiorization of cognitive-methodological knowledge of future teachers through emotional perception, artistic creativity, and reflection. During the research process, a specific set of methods was applied, taking into account the specific nature of each stage of competence development:

- Introductory cognitive methods: conversation, lecture, discussion, polylogue, motivational dialogue, modeling activities related to moral culture;
- Methods of stimulating activity and behavior: illustration, demonstration, dramatized games, exercises, activity encouragement methods, completion of group learning projects, reflection of behavior;
- Methods for forming emotional and evaluative attitudes toward activity: emotional impact methods, observation and emotional perception of cultural activities, cultural dialogue;
- Methods of engaging students in moral and cultural activities: emotional influence, situations of creative exploration, situations supporting free choice, situations of moral-ethical decision-making and collaborative problem-solving activities.

The use of the latest tools and methods of information delivery, namely the integration of computers and information technologies into the educational process, is increasingly important. Based on the above conceptual approaches, as well as the structure, content, and

volume of instructional information in the course “*Economic Theory*,” the following teaching methods and tools were selected.

Teaching methods and techniques: communication, case study, problem-based method, educational games, “brainstorming,” “insert,” “We learn together,” “pinboard,” and lectures (introductory lecture, visual lecture, thematic lecture, lecture-conference, case-solving lecture, pre-planned error lecture, review lecture, and concluding lecture).

Forms of organizing teaching: frontal, collective, group-based, dialogic, polylogical, and collaboration-based learning.

Teaching tools: in addition to traditional teaching aids (textbooks, lecture notes, reference outlines, overhead projector), graphic organizers, computers, and information technologies are used.

Means of interaction: diagnostics of teaching based on analysis of assessment results.

Methods and tools of management: planning of learning sessions in the form of technological maps, which define the stages of the lesson and ensure the joint activity of teachers and students in achieving learning objectives, as well as students’ independent work outside the classroom.

Monitoring and assessment: continuous monitoring of learning outcomes throughout the course, and assessment of student performance using a rating system for each session and for the entire academic year.

A lecture is a coherent, logically structured, and clear presentation of a scientific topic. It is one of the most effective and dynamic forms of interaction between the teacher’s personality—encompassing intellect, emotions, will, feelings, and beliefs—and the inner world of students. It helps realize the informational, methodological, guiding, and educational functions of teaching.

The guiding function of a lecture directs students’ attention to the key principles of the learning material, its role and significance in future professional activities, as well as the methods of mastering it. The informational function of a lecture is realized when the teacher explains the essence of key scientific facts, principles, and conclusions. The application of the methodological function of teaching helps to compare and contrast research methods and to identify the principles and approaches of scientific inquiry. The educational (upbringing) function is implemented through the formation of emotional evaluative attitudes toward the learning material, the development of interest, and the clarification of logical thinking and argumentation during the lecture process.

In teaching the subject of Philosophy, the use of the “Cluster” method plays an important role in systematizing students’ knowledge and ensuring its stability.

A cluster (from English *cluster* – meaning “group” or “network”) is a local technology that enables students to understand the interconnections between ideas, theories, laws, and concepts they have learned or will learn. It creates the basis for developing analytical and critical thinking skills by showing the continuity and interdependence of knowledge.

The process of creating a cluster is carried out as follows:

A key idea from the content of Philosophy is written in the center of the board or paper;

Concepts and laws related to this idea are connected using lines or arrows to show their interrelationships;

Then factual information related to these concepts and laws is added in a graphical form, forming a network structure;

Finally, conclusions are drawn about the connections between previously studied topics and the new topic being learned.

CONCLUSION. The motivational component of developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers in teaching Philosophy includes a positive and creative attitude toward professional activity. The structure of the motivational component is based on the presence of a stable and meaningful interest in professional values. Theoretical and methodological approaches to developing cognitive-methodological competence of future teachers in teaching Philosophy have led to the need for modeling this process.

The main reason for choosing the modeling method in this research is that it allows for a clear understanding of the dialectical interrelation between subsystem elements of cognitive-methodological competence development. From a philosophical perspective, cognitive-methodological knowledge serves as a key concept for describing the speed, effectiveness, and specificity of the development of this system, as well as the ability to perceive and apply values in practice. In addition, it also defines the psychological mechanism that ensures this process—reflection

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